

Narrative of the Third World: A Study of Mamang Dai's Legends of Pensam

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Abstract:

Mamang Dai's Legends of Pensam is a literary exploration of the Third World that delves into the profound narrative world created by Mamang Dai, a skilled writer from India's Northeastern region. The study critically examines the novel Legends of Pensam, which serves as a rich tapestry interweaving themes of identity, tradition, and contemporary challenges faced by indigenous communities. Set against the Himalayan backdrop of Arunachal Pradesh, Dai's work provides a unique perspective within postcolonial literature, offering a lesser-explored dimension of the Third World narrative. The study's focus can be encapsulated in several key areas.

Firstly, it delves into the cultural reverberations of Legends of Pensam. The novel immerses readers in the cultural vibrancy of Arunachal Pradesh, shedding light on indigenous traditions and rituals. The study examines how Dai's narrative constructs a bridge between oral traditions and contemporary storytelling, preserving cultural legacies while navigating the winds of change. Secondly, the study probes into the themes of identity and belonging. It explores the multifaceted nature of identity among the residents of Pensam, grappling with questions of belonging and rootedness in the face of modernization. Dai's narrative poignantly illustrates how the preservation of cultural identity serves as both a source of strength and a challenge in a rapidly evolving world. Lastly, the study underscores the ecological resonance within the narrative. The pristine landscapes of Arunachal Pradesh are more than just a backdrop; they are integral to the narrative's ecological consciousness. This article dissects how the narrative emphasizes the delicate ecological balance and its intrinsic connection to the lives and traditions of the people of Pensam.

Mamang Dai's Legends of Pensam offers a rich tapestry of cultural exploration, identity, and ecological awareness within the context of the Third World narrative. This study critically analyzes these facets, shedding light on how Dai's work contributes to the broader understanding of the complexities and cultural richness of the region.

Keywords: Northeast writings, Third World narrative, cultural richness, identity, cultural legacies, traditions etc.

Mamang Dai is a renowned female author hailing from the northeastern region of India.

The individual in question was born in the year 1957 in Pasighat, a town located in the state of

Arunachal Pradesh. The individual in question is a multi-faceted professional, encompassing the roles of a journalist, an Indian poet, and a writer. Their professional activities are mostly centred in Itanagar, located in Arunachal Pradesh. She is a member of the Adi tribe indigenous to the region. Upon the conclusion of her education at Pine Mount School in Shillong, she pursued her undergraduate studies in English literature at Gauhati University. In 1979, she became the first woman from her state to be chosen for the Indian Administrative Service (IAS). However, her passion for journalism drove her to relinquish this position and instead pursue a career in journalism. As a journalist, she had positions at esteemed publications such as The Telegraph, Hindustan Times, and The Sentinel.

Additionally, she was a programme officer at the World Wide Fund for Nature. She is the President of the Arunachal Pradesh Union of Working Journalists. The individual in question has produced a diverse range of literary works, encompassing fiction and non-fiction genres and poetry. The author has published two non-fiction works, namely Arunachal Pradesh: *The Hidden Land* (2003) and *Mountain Harvest: The Food of Arunachal* (2004). *The Sky Queen* and *Once Upon A Moontime* (2003) is a folklore text authored and illustrated by the individual in question. Some of her poetry volumes are *The River Poem* (2004), *Hambreelsai's Loom* (2014), and *Midsummer Survival Lyric* (2014). The author's initial literary work, *The Legends of Pensam*, was released in 2006, followed by the publication of another novel, *Stupid Cupid*, in 2008, and finally, *The Black Hill* in 2014.

Narrative of the third world in The Legends of Pensam :

This study focuses on narratives about the supernatural realm, namely within Mamang Dai's work, *The Legends of Pensam*, which explores themes of the third world. The literary work encompasses a collection of narratives that explore the experiences and circumstances of three successive generations residing in a rural community in Arunachal Pradesh. The author of this literary work has skillfully integrated traditional folklore and superstitious beliefs into the fabric of the villagers' lives. Dai has structured the novel into four distinct sections, which are titled as follows: "A Diary of the World," "Songs of the Rhapsodist," "Daughters of the Village," and "A Matter of Time."

The next sections discuss different narratives about the harmonious relationship between humans and nature that existed before colonial governance since the Adis adhered to

an animistic belief system that revolved around forest ecology and the symbiotic coexistence with the natural environment.

In addition to the realms of human existence and the natural environment, the narratives also depict the existence of a third realm, namely the spiritual realm. A spiritual realm was once prominent, with a harmonious coexistence between this realm, humanity, and the natural world. According to the author, individuals experience premonitions within these diminutive clearings amidst the jungle. Women can envision and aspire towards many dreams. Infants are born with an accelerated growth rate comparable to deer or lion cubs. The character Hoxo serves as the central figure in the narratives, commonly referred to as "the boy who descended from the heavens," (10) as depicted in the initial tale of the literary work. The descent of a male individual from the atmosphere and its subsequent embrace by a pair of individuals represents the tribe's willingness to acknowledge the existence of an unseen and intangible realm. In the same narrative, the author recounts another event wherein Hoxo and his companion Rakut overheard their fathers engaging in a conversation that struck them as peculiar. Hoxo's father recounts the event by stating, "I perceived a distinct sound of water splashing, prompting me to turn my gaze towards the source. To my astonishment, I observed the river's edge being elevated, causing the water to cascade from the posterior region of a lengthy, gleaming creature, resembling either a fish or a serpent." (9) Subsequently, it vanished without delay. All those in attendance believed as they knew of the existence of the water serpent, Biribik. The visual phenomenon seen by Hoxo's father functioned as an indication of an impending occurrence that was either negative or deviated from the natural order. Subsequently, Hoxo's father met his demise in an incident that transpired during a hunting expedition. It was anticipated that a tragic event would occur. The user did not provide any text to rewrite.

In the narrative titled "The Silence of Adela and Kepi," Mona, the individual who owns a publication known as Diary of the World, which specialises in featuring extraordinary real-life accounts, engaged in a conversation with Hoxo regarding her daughter Adela, who had recently received a diagnosis of autism, a perplexing medical condition. According to Mona, on a particular occasion, she encountered a situation when her attempts to engage in conversation with her daughter were met with refusal on her daughter's part. Mona assumed a crouching position adjacent to the girl, attempting to elicit verbal communication from her. However, the girl maintained a prolonged gaze before afterwards averting her gaze as if she

had no prior recollection of Mona's presence. During their conversation, Hoxo informs Mona about a parallel incident involving a little child named Kepi, which occurred concurrently with Adela's departure from the world. Hoxo knew about the concept of Kepi, as he was summoned to preside over a ceremonial event to discern whether Kepi was under the influence of supernatural entities. Hoxo provided an account of the child's condition during which his parents sought out shamans. Throughout the duration, the infant remained still yet engaged in activities such as crying, eating, and sleeping while maintaining a rigid and immobile torso posture. The individuals in question consistently transported him to various locations. Subsequently, an individual suggested that it would be prudent to contemplate conducting a distinctive ritual, which is infrequently observed in contemporary times, if the entity responsible for encircling their son's body was a serpent's spirit. According to Hoxo, it is evident that Kepi's father, Togum, bears responsibility for Kepi's current state.

The author describes an instance where he observed Togum venturing into the forest's heart to access the timber stockpile. Togum became aware of the presence of a snake that had taken up residence inside the vicinity of the logs. The individual made the necessary preparations for the hunting expedition; nevertheless, he was overcome with intense emotion upon witnessing the scene. The individual initially believed the creature to be a king cobra. Still, upon closer examination, they discovered that it possessed a captivating appearance characterised by a combination of gold, green, and dark amethyst hues. The creature's appearance was dynamic, exhibiting a remarkable radiance that defied adequate description. I apologise, but you have not provided any text for me to rewrite. Despite being captivated by the visual spectacle, he discharged his weapon and, in collaboration with his companions, investigated the consequences of his actions. The physical presence of the snake had a profound effect on Togum. As the snake's body continued to move, Togum observed a remarkable decrease in its dazzling appearance, coinciding with a perceived reduction in the intensity of sunshine and the vibrancy of the surrounding green forest. This is the reason why the serpent ritual needed to be conducted. I apologise, but you have not provided any text for me to rewrite.

In the narrative of "Pinyar," the author describes a mythical group known as the miti-mili, who inhabited a bygone era. (28) These entities formerly produced an enigmatic substance known as si-ye, which they distributed to humanity before they vanished. It was exclusively assigned to women, and Pinyar was known for her exceptional skills in producing si-ye cakes.

It is often postulated that an evil entity resides within the si-ye, purported to induce a state of insanity in individuals. This practice involves the application of si-ye onto the eyelids of individuals who have experienced an untimely demise to prevent the potential return of their souls to a state of restlessness.

Pinyar informed Mona and Hoxo that his son is currently experiencing paranormal disturbances attributed to the neglect of specific rituals in previous instances. The error can be attributed to the actions of our predecessors, including our parents and grandparents. I also made an error. A gathering of esteemed religious leaders is anticipated to convene to perform a ceremonial expulsion of an evil entity. I have initiated communication with them by telephone." (17) When individuals became aware that Kamur, the son of Pinyar, perpetrated an assault against his wife and daughter, it is commonly assumed that some form of enchantment or bewitchment likely influenced his actions. It is plausible to suggest that an evil entity may have engaged in a transaction involving the relinquishment of his spiritual essence in exchange for the occurrence of a profoundly distressing event. This event transpired during a specific hour, whereby the entity above, armed with a deteriorated Dao, pursued his offspring and spouse. It is worth noting that the wife's unbound tresses seemingly diverted the impact of a potentially fatal strike, preserving her life.

Similarly to Pinyar, some also said, "He should not be held accountable." (18) It is a hereditary trait. There exist individuals, both male and female, who possess the knowledge and expertise to discern this particular flaw within one's lineage.. In elucidating and deliberating about the course above of action, it has been posited that certain bloodlines are deemed highly sensitive and are subject to a near-taboo status in discourse. They see visual phenomena. The individuals in question have visitations from ethereal entities, such as the mini-mill, which induce episodes of mental instability afterwards. The user did not provide any text to rewrite.

In the narrative titled "The Heart of the Insect," Dai recounts the presence of "Dimi tayang," a solitary spiritual being that agitates the lake's waters and ensnares intruding individuals within a frigid embrace. (59) Travellers who venture into hilly or mountainous regions often pray for their safe voyage, as they believe that such environments pose potential risks to their lives. They are aware of the presence of rivers that possess a voracious appetite for human lives and mountains that loom ominously, capable of depriving them of their breath. The gusty wind emitted a shrill sound and taunted the individuals, attempting to deprive them

of their perception. The rice they transported transformed, resulting in a hardened texture resembling individual grains. I apologise, but you have not provided any text for me to rewrite. To ensure their secure return, it is imperative for the individuals to effectively persuade the "jealous spirits" (59) to permit them to reach their intended destination safely.

The narrative of "A Homecoming" explores the customary practises of the tribe or clan in making offerings to foster harmony across the realms. The author provides a narrative in which they describe that,

A shaman was summoned, and the ceremonial proceedings commenced with the performance of ritualistic chants, invoking the spirits to communicate and reveal their desires. The transaction can be characterised as a mutually beneficial exchange of goods or services at a favourable price. We shall engage in the process of slaughtering chickens and thereafter proceed to produce delectable cuisine for your consumption. The proposed action involves the pouring of wine onto the stones, so imbuing the surrounding environment with the aroma of blood and ginger. We shall adhere to societal prohibitions and uphold tranquilly. (85)

In ancient times, individuals often carried ginger to safeguard themselves during their journeys, which was believed to possess potent medicinal properties capable of warding off evil spirits. (94) Any occurrence that deviated from the ordinary was attributed to the actions of these spirits, who sought retribution or punishment for the failure to fulfil certain rituals by members of the clan or tribe.

Conclusion:

These anecdotes serve as evidence of the presence of the third world, specifically the supernatural realm, in the lives of individuals. Dai's narratives underscore the importance of coherence across all existent realms. The spiritual realm also exhibits a desire for attention and respect. When practices or rituals neglect this realm, spirits may express their anger by either luring someone to their demise during a hunting expedition or travel or exerting power over them. Consequently, the author meticulously and profoundly delineates the importance and consequences of the supernatural realm in the everyday existence of individuals through these narratives.

Dai employs the flashback technique to recollect the narratives, and she proceeds to narrate the tales by utilising the persona of Hoxo. Hoxo assumes the role of narrator as he recounts the events to Mona, who serves as the proprietor of a sophisticated publication known as *Diary of the World*. This magazine specialises in featuring extraordinary real-life stories. The age range being referred to is between 17 and 18 years old. The novel employs a narrative method utilised by Hoxo to advance the plot. The narratives inside the novel are presented in a first-person perspective, introducing a sense of subjectivity. The author's place of birth is Arunachal Pradesh. Consequently, it may be inferred that the author is portraying the customs, traditions, and rituals practised in that particular region and sharing personal accounts of witnessing or hearing stories about the spirits. Dai employs lowercase titles for all of her works, signifying her aesthetic distinctiveness as an author.

References

Dai, Mamang *The Legends of Pensam*. Penguin Books India. 2006. Print.

Raatan, T. *History, Religion, Culture of North East India*, Isha Books, Delhi. 2006. Print.

Swami, Indu. *Exploring North-east Indian Writings in English*. Sarup Book Publishers Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi. 2011. Print.